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ABSTRACT: *The paper explores the difficulties of substantiation of adjectives in modern english. In the paper, the study of adjectives' functions and the process of substantivation described in the literature on this topic is discussed.*

Key words: *nationality, noun, adjective, verb, predicative, term, function, basic, conversion.*

We've chosen this term because we like adjectives from our early school years. We were fascinated by adjectives and to discover something we didn't know before. We first learned the basical terms of adjectives in order to describe it as part of speech. To complete our course work, we used many theoretical textbooks, such as: « modern english language» v.n. : I.p. zhigadlo, i.p. Ivanova, I.I. Baker, mark. : moscow, moscow. Verbs, nouns, and adjectives are included in the lexical categories. Cambridge university press, etc. We then turned to the “warren, beatrice.” Adjectives are used to describe a subject. To get to know their theories and perceptions about adjectives as a part of expression, gothenburg uses english as a language. Here's what we learned about it: an adjective is a term used to describe a noun or a pronoun in english, usually by describing it or making its meaning more specific. In the majority of languages, adjectives exist. In english, the most commonly used terms are people, places, or things such as big, old, and tired. Some grammarians classify the words a, an, and and possessive nouns, such as mary's, as adjectives; however, such classification may be specific to one language. Such noun modifiers are used by other grammarians to determine the meaning of a sentence. In the same way, possessive adjectives, such as his or her, are sometimes called determinative possessive pronouns, and demonstrative adjectives, such as this or that, are often called determinative demonstratives. Participles are used as adjectives in some languages. The term lingering headache and broken toys are two examples of participles used as adjectives. Modifying nouns, adjectively used, or just part of a compound noun, are sometimes called modifying nouns, or nouns used

adjectivally. Adjectives. Adjectives are the third major class of words in english, after nouns and verbs, according to dixon's theory.

Adjectives are terms that describe the properties of objects, such as: adverbs are words that describe a person's personality. Large, blue, productive, etc.) and, therefore, qualifying nouns. adjectives in english do not change by number or case. They only have a grammatical unit, the degrees of comparison. They are also characterized by the words' functions. Adjectives are substantivized. Often, terms are substantiated. In this case, they have the functions of nouns in the sentence and are always preceded by the definite word. Substantivized adjectives have two meanings: 1) they can refer to a group of individuals in a general sense (e.g., a person). The poor are poor people, the dead are poor people, and the sick are dead people, etc.) Such adjectives have a plural root meaning and are often used to describe a plural word. E.g., a smear of the word "sea" on a computer. The elderly are entitled to a pension. The young aren't they? In special schools, the blind are trained in skills. If we want to denote a single individual, we must include a noun. E.g., a smear of the word "sea" on a computer. The old man receives a pension. It is also necessary to include a noun if we want to refer to a particular group of people (not the whole group). E.g., a smear of the word "sea" on a computer. The young are usually intolerable. The young men are fishermen. Several adjectives denoting nationalities (e.g., ", ', etc.) are used to describe nationalities. The same is true for english, french, and dutch. E.g., a smear of the word "sea" on a computer. The english are huge tea lovers. Among the visitors were a few english people. 3) substantivized adjectives can also refer to an abstract idea. They are then singular in form and form a singular verb. E.g., a smear of the word "sea" on a computer. The good in him outweighs the bad. My mother never lost her love of the extravagant. Adjectives' syntactic functions are discussed in this paper. In the sentence, adjectives can be used as follows: 1) an attribute, e.g., a number. Do you remember the small green boat with the odd shape? In the windy darkness, the farm's lights flashed out. Adjectives that appear as terms are usually followed by the noun. There is no pause between the verb and the noun in the case of a plural.

These attributes are called close attributes. However, an adjective that is in preposition to the noun can be separated from it by a pause. It becomes a loose attribute as a result. E.g., a smear of the word "sea" on a computer. George listened to my story with awe and compassion, and he understood it with utmost care. However, loose attributes are more commonly found in the post-position to the noun. E.g., a smear of the word "sea" on a computer. My father, happy and drained, kissed me goodnight. 2) a predicative, e.g., a syllable. Her expression was almost professional. He seemed

mature, sober, and calm. 3) is a part of a compound verbal predicate, e.g. He stood still, his back turning to the side, as he sat down. She lay motionless, as if she were asleep. 4) an objective predicative, e.g., a syllable. I thought he was very intelligent. She wore her hair short. 5) a subjective predicative, e.g. The door was locked tightly. Her hair was dyed blonde. Most adjectives can be used both attributively and predicatively, but some, including those beginning with a-, can only be used as predicative (e.g. a-). (ask, asleep, along, alive, alert, alert, ashamed, and also content, sorry, sick, due, etc.) A few adjectives can only be used as attributes, e.g. : Outer, major, minor, only, whole, former, latter, and some others) are included in this list. Adjectives were the subject of our investigation. Adjectives have comparative and superlative forms, as we have discovered in english. They are usually expressed in one of two ways: by suffixes (big, bigger, and bigger) or by the use of the grammatical particles that are used the most. In their analysis, we have found that some adjectives have suppletive forms, such as good, better, and the best. The comparative and superlative forms refer only to the base form of the word, so duplicate forms such as the most important or worsen are nonstandard. There is no such thing as a comparative as a superlative with the letter "m": the uppermost, the westernmost, etc. It also has its own degrees, such as comparison, etc. Those that have "absolute" characteristics, such as male, female, extinct, and extinct, do not accept comparisons: one animal cannot be more extinct than another. In a planktonic organism, the term planktonic simply refers to a planktonic organism; there are no degrees or grades of planktonic. Other situations are more difficult to answer.

Grammatical prescriptivists object to terms such as more perfect on the grounds that something is either perfect or it is not. However, many english speakers tend to interpret the term as more than perfect. In this regard, an adjective that sparks a lot of controversy is not unusual. Purists are bound to find the more unusual and unique formulations that will lift their hackles. Which english adjectives are compared by -er/-est and which by more/most is a complicated matter of english idiom. Shorter adjectives (including the most monosyllabic adjectives), anglo-saxon words, and shorter, fully domesticated french words are generally used. Noble) use the suffixes -er/-est. Adjectives with two syllables are different. Some are available in either form, and the situation dictates the order in which they are used. According to the situation, one will see something that is more common and more common. Two-syllable adjectives that end in the letter i, most commonly spelled with y, are characterized by the letters -er/-est, e.g., pretty : prettier : prettiest. It was enjoyable to study adjectives, but we think that this isn't the end of its investigation.

References

1. Abduraxmanova, Z., & Mamurova, M. (2021). THEORETICAL APPROACH TO SPEECH DISFLUENCIES IN SIMULTANEOUS INTERPRETATION. In МОЛОДОЙ ИССЛЕДОВАТЕЛЬ: ВЫЗОВЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ (pp. 43-45).
2. Абдурахманова, З. (2022). Analysis of pauses and interruptions as elements of linguistic production in simultaneous interpretation. Современные инновационные исследования актуальные проблемы и развитие тенденции: решения и перспективы, 1(1), 533-535.
3. Dildora Q., Barchinoy N., Muhammad F. AYTILGAN SINF: FAOLI, SAMARALI VA MUSTAHKAMLANGAN O'QITISH-XAXSUS TO'LIQ O'G'ILGANLAR UCHUN //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – S. 358-364.
4. International Conference on Multidisciplinary Research 1 (1), 140-143, 2023 Zilola A., Barchinoy N., Muhammad F. THE ROLE OF MEDIA IN INFLUENCING CULTURE AND SOCIETY //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 190-197.
5. Zilola A. et al. ANALYSES OF ADS //International conference on multidisciplinary science. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 5. – С. 66-69.
6. Zilola A. et al. ANALYSIS OF POEM //" XXI ASRDA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALAR, FAN VA TA'LIM TARAQQIYOTIDAGI DOLZARB MUAMMOLAR" nomli respublika ilmiy-amaliy konferensiyasi. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 11. – С. 14-18
7. Mokhira, K. (2023). THE IMPORTANCE OF DIFFERENT SUB-SKILLS THAT ARE INVOLVED IN PARTICIPATING IN A GROUP DISCUSSION. *International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research*, 496-499.
8. Mokhira, K. (2023). HOLISTIC SCORING AS A GRADING METHOD. *International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research*, 493-495.
9. Khusanova, M. (2022). Learning new content material through cooperative group discussions. *European Scholar Journal*, 3, 44-45.